

8T –The Graviton Rise

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial coupling constants series author will cover a set of theoretical options. These options are describing the potential rise of the Graviton and serve as a set of predictions to experimental physicist.

Introduction

The 8T is a the theory of variational curvature, the main equation (1) is describing the principle of equivalence between gravity and acceleration, and by demanding the two conditions $\partial g / \partial t = 0$ and $\frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$ we have the conditions to "dark energy" which Is the result of distinct manifolds interacting in areas of extremum curvatures, leading to an acceleration from those areas, and

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.42) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term of equation (1) and derived the existence of Fermions. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \tag{1.47}$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \tag{1.48}$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matrix tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \tag{1.49}$$

The Graviton in the 8T is represented by a combination of three Bosons and one Lepton, i.e. the electron, even though due to the EMT symmetry it can be the Muon of the Tao. The following form is the structure of the graviton:

$$[(2N_{gravity}) + (3)] + N_{V1} + N_{V2} + N_{V3} = \left[2N_{gravity} + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \quad (2.2)$$

It recently became evident to one that there could be a several forms in which we can represent gravity which exceeds the invariance of spin due to replacing the Bosons. A more interesting form of Gravitons includes timed emission of two Bosons from two distinct Leptons which aspire to "stay away" from each other, or to obey the Pauli exclusion Principle.

$$\left[2N_{gravity} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} = [(2N_{gravity}) + (3) + (3)] + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \quad (2.2.A)$$

To emphasize the idea of the Leptons to be different state it is possible to map them in different directions ensuring they will never vanish into an even number and ruin the coupling series:

$$[(2N_{gravity}) + (3) + (3)] + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \rightarrow [(2N_{gravity}) + (\vec{3}) + (\vec{3})] + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \quad (2.2.B)$$

So that is a much simpler version than the first which is represented in the 8T thesis. First, it balance out the inequality between the Lepton and the Bosons in the coupling term. Instead of having one Lepton to generate three Bosons, we require now two Leptons to generate one Boson each. Than the summation of spin accumulates to spin two. The actual type of the Boson is not relevant to this discussion, for simplicity sake it can be the photon.

$$[(2N_{gravity}) + (\vec{3}) + (\vec{3})] + \gamma + +\gamma \rightarrow [(2N_{gravity}) + (\vec{e}) + (\vec{e})] + \gamma + \gamma \quad (2.2.C)$$

So the result of (2.2. C) than accumulate to an even number which in variation from can be ignored, as it vanishes. The result is one term in the coupling of Gravity similar to the coupling of the strong which contain only one term. The one term indicate that similar to the Boson of the Strong, the Graviton is massless and it is short range.

$$[(2N_{gravity}) + (\vec{e}) + (\vec{e})] + \gamma + \gamma \rightarrow (2N_{gravity}) + Even \quad (2.4)$$

$$(2N_{gravity}) + Even \rightarrow (2N_{gravity}) \quad (2.41)$$

Another option of the rise of the Graviton, which is the last option, as far as one can see, is the result of three Leptons and one Boson, which will again lead to equation (2.4) and (2.41):

$$[(2N_{gravity}) + (\vec{3}) + (\vec{3}) + (\vec{3})] + N_{V1} \rightarrow [(2N_{gravity}) + (\vec{e}) + (\vec{e}) + (\vec{e})] + \gamma$$

These forms of gravity indicate that the Graviton is more likely to rise in elements with large number of Leptons, i.e. heavy elements, when we have the balanced form of Gravitons, those Bosons have to be timed, that is to be propagated in the same temporal segment for some arbitrary frame of reference.

$$[(2N_{gravity}) + (\vec{e}) + (\vec{e})] + \gamma + \gamma \rightarrow [(2N_{gravity}) + (\vec{e}) + (\vec{e})] + \gamma_{t_1} + \gamma_{t_2} \quad (2.42)$$

$$t_1 = t_2$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

M. Ohad's Theory